

Materials Modelling and Informatics Software Market

AN ADVANCED INSIGHT INTO THE MARKET LANDSCAPE

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Table of Contents

1.	Introduction.....	2
2.	Definition and Overview of Sectors.....	2
3.	Market Size Headlines	3
4.	Materials Modelling Market Analysis.....	5
	Market Sectors and Size	5
	Distribution of Materials Modelling Sectors Across Companies.....	6
	Size of Companies in Materials Modelling Market.....	7
	Free and Open-Source Software for Materials Modelling	8
	Quantum Computing Based Materials Modelling Software	8
5.	Materials Informatics Market Analysis.....	9
	Company Size and Revenue Distribution	10
6.	Conclusions and Outlook.....	12
7.	Acknowledgements	12
8.	Disclaimer	12
9.	Abbreviations.....	13
10.	References	14
11.	Appendix A: Methodology.....	16
	11.1. General	16
	11.2. Market Specific – Materials Modelling.....	16
	11.3. Market Specific – Materials Informatics.....	17
12.	Appendix B: Materials Modelling Software Providers	18
	12.1. Small Enterprises	18
	12.2. Medium Enterprises	20
	12.3. Large Enterprises	20
	12.4. Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS).....	21
	<i>The FOSS Electronic Modelling Market.....</i>	21
	<i>The FOSS Atomistic Modelling Market</i>	21
	<i>The FOSS Mesoscopic Modelling Market.....</i>	22
	<i>The FOSS Continuum Modelling Market.....</i>	22
13.	Appendix C: Quantum Computing Enterprises	23
14.	Appendix D: Materials Informatics Software Providers	23
	14.1. Small Enterprises	23
	14.2. Medium Enterprises	24
	14.3. Large Enterprises	24

1. Introduction

Materials play a pivotal role in a multitude of challenges facing our planet and societies, including safety and sustainability, resilience of supplies and manufacturing as well as ever increasing demands on their properties and functions. Across all sectors, advances in materials are required to address issues, such as sustainability, resourcing, recycling, safety, and numerous structural and functional performance criteria. The complexity of requirements, huge potential design space and required shortened development cycles of materials cannot be addressed by traditional research and development approaches. In response, methodologies, like model-based design and data-based methods that include machine learning and AI are being more widely deployed and integrated. The markets in pertinent technologies such as materials modelling have seen significant merger and acquisition (M&A) activities as large product lifecycle management (PLM) and engineering software providers acquire a range of 'niche' players in specific sectors of materials modelling and informatics. At the same time, due to the rapid development of data and modelling related technologies, such as machine learning (ML), artificial intelligence (AI), semantic technologies (Costello & van der Meulen, 2018) (Gartner, 2023) and quantum computing, the rate of new ventures entering the field remains high.

In response to this continued development and integration of data and model-based technologies for materials, we have been gradually increasing the scope of our market analysis. Our first report on the economic impact of molecular modelling of chemicals and materials (Goldbeck G. , 2012), was limited to 'discrete' materials modelling software (electronic, atomistic, and mesoscopic models). The estimated market size at the time was in the region of €50m with 10 key players. In 2020, we extended the scope of the market study (Goldbeck & Simperler, 2020) to include all types of modelling (i.e., continuum), applied to the study of materials and analysed the relevant activities of 72 software companies. This led to a total market size of about €340m, with a share of about 25% (€85m) in discrete modelling. Here we saw that a much larger, industrially significant part of materials modelling utilized typical engineering codes, e.g., based on Finite Element Modelling (FEM) techniques. Another key finding was that large enterprises dominate the continuum modelling software market, with about 89% of the market share, whereas in the discrete modelling field, SMEs still make up >40% of the market, despite some M&A consolidation.

In this study, we update our 2020 study in materials modelling to include a total of 98 software providers. Furthermore, we extend the scope to include the field of materials informatics, including its sub-sectors of data content, data and information management, and materials modelling solutions based on data-based models, machine learning and artificial intelligence. In total, we include 38 companies in this section.

Finally, we introduce the nascent market in quantum-computing solutions for computational chemistry, with nine companies included. Providers are largely in the development phase, but applications are emerging.

2. Definition and Overview of Sectors

The scope of this study includes all modelling and informatics-based software with applications in chemistry, materials science, and engineering.

Materials modelling software markets include the use of any physics-based or data-based model to studying the behaviour of chemicals and materials either on their own or in processes and products. The key is that materials rather than say engineered products, should be the subject of study and a simulation delivers new data and properties about the material under consideration as an output. For reference, physics-based models are based on fundamental physics equations for electron, atom, mesoscopic and continuum volume entities, (CWA 17284 , 2018) whereas data-based models are entirely based on empirical relations derived and/or parameterised from datasets, or any ML or AI method, respectively. (de Baas, 2014) .

Materials Informatics applies the principles of informatics to materials science and engineering to support the discovery, development, selection, formulation, and application of materials. Informatics in this context

means the practice of creating, storing, finding, manipulating, and sharing data and information. In the context of materials informatics, sources of data and information include characterisation, increasingly also based on high-throughput methods and robotics, as well as materials modelling. As in modelling, we include chemistry-related methods, such as cheminformatics, in which used in the study of materials, i.e., outside of life sciences.

An overview of the different fields that contribute to market sectors is shown in Figure 1. In the modelling sector, we distinguish between discrete and continuum physic-based models (see (CWA 17284 , 2018) and (de Baas, 2014)). In addition, there are empirical data-based modelling methods and more ‘traditional’ ML methods, such as QSPR that are often included in materials modelling software packages and we do not specifically break out that sub-sector of the market, i.e., their contributions will be included in the physics-based market size. However, more recent ML/AI-based software for materials, which is typically packaged with other data and information management methods, is attributed to the materials informatics market. Furthermore, the informatics market includes the proportion of cheminformatics applied to materials, materials data content and materials information management systems. For the latter, there is the emerging field of materials ontologies. However, there are few established companies to date. We intend to quantify that sub-sector in a future study. Here, we take a first look at the emerging business in quantum computing for chemicals and materials and include an estimate of its market size.

Figure 1. Overview of different materials modelling and informatics fields, including physics-based materials modelling with either discrete entities (electrons, atoms, mesoscopic entities) or continuum volumes, data-based modelling, including empirical equation-based methods, surrogate methods, ML and AI approaches. Data content and management of materials information are included, typically using databases and, more recently, extending to knowledge management using ontologies.

3. Market Size Headlines

We estimate the overall market size of materials modelling and informatics software in 2022 (Figure 2) to be ≈€659.1m, broken down into €383.3m for continuum materials modelling, €120.3m for discrete materials modelling (including a quantum computing based software contribution of €13.7m) and €155.5m for materials informatics.

Figure 2. Overall market size of continuum and discrete materials modelling, and materials informatics software in 2022

The market size for materials modelling software is estimated to be €489.9m, based on an analysis that includes major companies and a relatively large number of small companies (total 98). The estimated value of discrete modelling is €106.6m (excluding quantum computing), i.e., ≈22% of continuum materials modelling. Big enterprises focus more on engineering modelling, like PLM, so the materials modelling market is dominated by a large number of small enterprises (up to 50 employees) that make up ≈76.5 % of the players, and most business located in the €1–5m range, both for discrete and continuum modelling.

Regarding market growth, we used the conservative figure of 7% per annum from 2019 to 2022 because COVID-19 and recession in recent years as a result of geopolitical circumstances may have hampered the growth. However, we are not far off as the global computer-aided design (CAD), computer aided manufacturing (CAM) and computer aided-engineering (CAE) Software Market (2022–2027) (Infogence Global Research, 2022) is expected to grow with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8%.

Quantum computing has yet to adopt a leading role in materials modelling, and some chemical and physical phenomena will greatly profit from the advent of more and more tools. So far, we can see a market size estimate of about €13.7m. As expected, this is the fastest growing market with a CAGR of ≈36%. (Precedence Research, 2022)

Materials informatics market size is estimated to be €155.5m. Parts of the materials informatics market are driven by the growth in ML/AI techniques, whereas others relate to digitalisation, for example in the context of Materials Acceleration Platforms (Flores-Leonar, et al., 2020) and ‘self-driving’ laboratories (Häse, Roch, & Aspuru-Guzik, 2019). These developments attract both new software ventures and new markets for established cheminformatics companies. Note that cheminformatics, a multi-billion Euro, largely life science dominated market, is expected to continue at a high CAGR of ≈15.5% for the period 2022–2027 (Mordor Intelligence, 2023). A recent analysis (Markets and Markets, 2023) concentrating on the materials informatics market predicts a similarly high CAGR of 16.3%, based on a market size of \$129m (≈€120m) in 2023. The market size figure is consistent with our estimate; our €35.5m larger estimate may be due to including a portion of cheminformatics providers that serve materials markets. The strong growth, likewise, is consistent with our observations of strong growth of individual companies in the sector.

4. Materials Modelling Market Analysis

Market Sectors and Size

The analysis is based on 98 software companies (see Appendix B). It includes 18 large, five medium and 75 small software providers¹ that offer software in at least one of the fields of materials modelling (see Figure 1). For companies with a wide range of software products (e.g., covering CAE and various informatics applications) and covering diverse markets, we identified the materials-relevant applications and their estimated share of revenue. Such delineation was in particular carried out in the following cases.

- Several software packages have both materials and life-science applications. This pertains to discrete modelling methods, such as electronic and atomistic models. Note that pharmaceutical development (from molecule to drug product) is included as a materials sector.
- In continuum modelling the boundary between materials and engineering modelling is fluid. Here we aim to identify applications that have a materials-focus and estimate the related market share. Wherever possible this was done in a bottom-up way, by identifying relevant software and their markets.
- In electronics, a significant part of technology computer-aided design (TCAD) is about the modelling of semiconductor materials and their structural properties and electrical behaviour in devices and is therefore included in the materials modelling market. In fact, this is an area in which continuum and discrete materials modelling is becoming increasingly integrated as the major players offer both the traditional continuum solutions as well as electronic modelling based TCAD.

Market size was determined as described in Appendix A. In particular, we assume growth of 7% on average for companies already included in our previous report and revisited their number of FTEs via personal contact, company webpages or Linked-In. We also analysed an additional 31 companies in total.

The resulting total materials modelling market size is €489.9 m, with discrete modelling software taking a share of ≈€106.6 m and continuum modelling ≈€383.3 m. The discrete modelling share of the market is about 22 % of the total (Figure 3).

Within the continuum market, we can also analyse specifically the materials-related TCAD market. Overall, the TCAD market size was valued at \$154.5m in 2019 (Grand View Research, 2020) with CAGR of 9.5%. Hence, we estimate the TCAD market size in 2022 as \$202.9m (€189m). Considering the materials modelling aspects, we researched Synopsis, Silvaco, and other SMEs, such as GlobalTCADSolutions, Crosslight, and Cogenda Software, and estimate a contribution of €20.7m to the overall materials modelling software market. Synopsis has the biggest share with 77%, followed by Silvaco with 12%, and the remaining SMEs take 11% of the share. With €20.7m of a total market of €189m, we estimate that materials aspects represent 11% of the total. This is higher than the average 8% assumed for CAE, but may also reflect the importance of materials design in TCAD.

¹ Small, Medium and Large enterprises are defined by the number of employees up 50, 250, or higher, respectively, see also https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/business-friendly-environment/sme-definition_en

Figure 3 The materials modelling market: (a) for discrete and continuum materials modelling in general, and (b) separating out the TCAD part of the continuum market.

Considering the CAE market as a whole and the proportion of materials modelling relative to global CAE market estimate we arrive at the following picture: Depending on the study, the global CAE market in 2022 was \$9.2bn (€8.57bn) according to (Grand View Research, 2023) or \$6.25bn (€5.82bn) according to Fortune Business Insights (Fortune Business Insights, 2022). Based on these figures, the materials modelling market represents 4.5–6.6% of the total CAE market.

Distribution of Materials Modelling Sectors Across Companies

Regarding the distribution of discrete and continuum modelling across companies, the market remains largely divided into companies offering either discrete or continuum materials modelling software but not both. As a result of the acquisition of Culgi by Siemens, there are now four companies offering discrete as well as continuum materials modelling software (Dassault Systemes, JSol/J-Octa, Siemens and Synopsys).

The distribution of companies offering discrete and continuum materials modelling, categorised by their materials modelling revenue, is shown in Figure 4. Note that revenue is not directly related to company size, because materials modelling is often just a (small) part of the business.

Figure 4 Materials modelling revenue distribution for providers of continuum, discrete, or both types of modelling software.

About 83% of all considered companies had estimated revenue of up to €5m related to materials modelling. The pure, discrete materials modelling software market is distributed across a wide range of players, up to €5m revenue, with only 10% in the €5–10m bracket. The picture is very different for the continuum modelling market in which providers feature in all revenue brackets. All of the providers of both materials modelling types are large enterprises.

Size of Companies in Materials Modelling Market

Considering company size (rather than materials modelling revenue as above), the distribution of the 98 companies by size (Figure 5) comprises 76.5% small, 5.1% medium and 18.4 % large enterprises.

Type of Enterprise/Number

Figure 5 Type of enterprises on the materials modelling software market

As in any business area, there is large proportion of small businesses. However, we see significant differences between the distribution in continuum and discrete materials modelling markets, respectively. Large enterprises have a dominant market share of continuum modelling (89.6%), whereas SMEs take the majority of the discrete modelling market (61.4%; Figure 6). Interestingly, there has been a relative increase in market share of SMEs since 2022, and we identified more SMEs with significant contributions and growth.

Figure 6 Market shares for the continuum and the discrete market: The continuum materials modelling market of the large enterprises is €343.5m and that of small and medium enterprises is €34.1m and €5.6m, respectively. For discrete modelling, the market of large enterprises is €45.2m, whereas the smaller companies take a share of €60.1m and the medium ones a share of €1.3m.

In Figure 7, we show the distribution by number of companies relative to their size, separately for continuum and discrete modelling providers. Note that here, the (few) companies that sell both software types are counted in both categories. Figure 7 shows that of the companies that offer continuum modelling, 38 (65.5%) are small enterprises, 4 (6.9%) are medium and 16 (27.6%) are large enterprises.

Figure 7 Enterprises offering (a) continuum and (b) discrete software, shown in number of companies

Figure 7 shows that for companies that sell discrete modelling software, the number of small enterprises is 37 (~84%). We infer from these figures that the discrete modelling market is far less consolidated than the continuum modelling market, which is supported by the above observation that few large CAE companies have integrated discrete modelling, whereas several have acquired pure-play continuum materials modelling companies. The proviso is that new and emerging materials modelling companies at the lower end of the market may have been missed from this analysis and many small CAE companies have not been included for which a fraction of business could be allocated to materials.

Free and Open-Source Software for Materials Modelling

In addition to commercial software, we investigated the level of economic activity related to free and open-source software (FOSS). Budgets to cover these are mostly provided by grant bodies in the case of FOSS. To estimate a monetary value (which by no means can provide a full estimate of economic value), we investigated the amount of investment required to cover staff costs and overheads for 60 companies we considered, listed in Appendix B. To simplify the data, we allocated € 150k per FTE to estimate their revenue and allowed for 7% annual growth. Numbers of staff were typically based on the number of developers, which can be obtained from websites and/or activity on public repositories, such as GitHub. Thus, the total “hidden” market we uncovered would contribute an additional €36m.

Quantum Computing Based Materials Modelling Software

Quantum computing is a rapidly growing sector that attracts enormous sums of public and private investment. Chemicals and materials are one of the key applications for which quantum computing can make a step change in speed and accuracy. Hence, many companies involved in quantum computing include potential materials applications, such as battery materials developments in their portfolio of interest. These

include very large enterprises, such as IBM² and Google³, and SMEs, such as IonQ, Quantum Brilliance and Rigetti.⁴

We focussed only on those companies that offer specific software geared towards chemicals and materials. Hence, we currently exclude companies with either a general hardware or software offering, even if they are involved in case examples and collaborations in materials, such as IBM with Bosch (IBM, 2022), and Riverlane with Johnson Matthey (Swayne, 2023).

Hence, as a basis for estimating the quantum computing based materials software market size in 2022, we assembled a list of five, relevant companies (HQS, Molecular Quantum Solutions, Quantinuum, Quantum Generative Materials/GenMat and QC Ware; see Appendix C). The list includes one large enterprise, two medium and two small providers.

Molecular Quantum Solutions allows users to define a material structure, simulate the lattices thereof and receive metrics to identify promising materials. QC Ware plans to offer “Chemistry Simulation” whereby users will be able to find the ground and excited states for photoactive molecules and calculate gradients and couplings of large molecules. Their other offers appeal to data scientist and quantum engineers, i.e., people who exploit the features of quantum mechanics to generate technical solutions surpassing the capabilities of classical computers. HQS explicitly offers software for materials scientists in the chemical industry and academia, and provide materials modelling solutions. Quantinuum, in addition to offering hardware solutions and cybersecurity applications, provides a computational chemistry solution called InQuanto™,⁵ which promises to enable computational chemists to work with a range of algorithms to solve quantum chemical problems. From these five contributors, we estimate a contribution to the materials modelling market of ≈€13.7m.

5. Materials Informatics Market Analysis

To estimate the materials informatics market size in 2022, we assembled a list of 39 companies (see Appendix D), including seven large, 12 medium and 20 small software providers that offer software in any of the informatics fields identified in Figure 1, i.e., ML/AI, information management and data content relevant to materials R&D. We also included organisations that provide cheminformatics products that are applied in the chemical materials field, i.e., outside of life sciences. Chem(o)informatics can be understood, according to Frank Brown (Brown, 1998), as the combination of “*all the information resources that a scientist needs to optimize the properties of a ligand to become a drug.*” However, some of these ligands (or better, chemicals) can also become a catalyst, a novel solvent, a building block of a metal organic framework, and so on, so the “information resources” can find an alternative use. For example, ≈ 20% of Dotmatics and ACD/Labs’ revenue is generated from materials informatics. The latter is defined as “*the application of data science, materials science, and machine learning to the materials and chemicals space*” according to Citrine Informatics⁶, who are dedicated 100% to materials and chemicals. For the cheminformatics organisations we researched the market segments of such companies and estimated the materials-related portion of the business.

² <https://www.ibm.com/quantum>

³ <https://quantumai.google/>

⁴ See <https://thequantuminsider.com/2022/09/05/quantum-computing-companies-ultimate-list-for-2022/> for an overview of quantum computing companies.

⁵ <https://www.quantinuum.com/news/by-chemists-for-chemists-introducing-inquanto-tm-2-0>

⁶ <https://citrine.io/what-is-materials-informatics/>

Considering all contributions, we estimate the total materials informatics market to be €155.5m. Similarly, a recent market analysis (Markets and Markets, 2023) concentrating on the materials informatics market predicts it to be \$129m in 2023 (≈€ 120m). In addition, we included a share of cheminformatics companies' revenues, which amounts to about €44m.

Sector analysis in the market was carried out as follows: We identified companies that were mainly active in ML/AI and data content. However, in information management, most companies are also active in other sectors. ML/AI solutions take a share of ≈€22.1m, materials data provision ≈€25.9m, and 'holistic' or general materials informatics solutions ≈€108.2m. The general providers' share of the market is ≈70% of the total (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The materials informatics market share for ML/AI (yellow), database (orange) and general materials informatics solutions (blue) providers.

Company Size and Revenue Distribution

Figure 9a shows the distribution of the revenue across companies. About 82% of the companies considered had estimated revenue of up to €5m related to materials informatics.

Figure 9. (a) Materials informatics market distribution by revenue range of providers and (b) type of enterprises on the materials informatics market

Our study includes 51.3% small, 30.8% medium and 17.9% large enterprises (Figure 9b)

In Figure 10, we can see that large enterprises dominate the market share of general materials informatics provisions (62%; €67.1 m). Companies that are predominantly in one of the sectors, i.e., data content and AI/ML tend to be smaller. Large companies take 17% (€4.43 m) of the materials data market, and do not feature on the ML/AI market, i.e., there are currently no large pure-play materials ML/AI enterprises.

Figure 10 Market shares for companies in ML/AI, materials data, and general materials informatics

The ML/AI market for medium enterprises is €16.4m and for small enterprises €5.1m. The medium-size organisations take €14.7m, which is the biggest share of the materials data market, whereas larger enterprises take €4.43m, which is less than small enterprises with a €6.8m share. Medium and small enterprises have comparable shares on the materials informatics market with €19.6m and €22.1m, respectively.

In Figure 11 we show the distribution by number of companies relative to their size, separately for ML/AI, materials data, and materials informatics provisions.

Figure 11. Enterprises offering ML/AI, data and materials informatics shown in number and size of companies

Of the materials ML/AI companies analysed, five (71%) are small and two (29%) are medium enterprises. For companies selling materials data, the number of small enterprises and medium enterprises is three, whereas the number of large enterprises is two. For companies selling materials informatics, the number of small enterprises is 12 (50%), of medium enterprises seven (29%), and the number of large enterprises is five (21%).

In contrast to the materials modelling market, which features a large proportion of small enterprises, materials informatics tends to feature a lower number of SMEs, hence a larger proportion of large companies. There may be various reasons for this difference including (a) we have not surveyed the field as extensively as for materials modelling, (b) materials modelling is based on advanced scientific developments over many decades, which have led to a wide range of startup companies whereas materials informatics is a more generic discipline with information science and ML/AI developments applied across the sectors. Therefore, transfer of technologies into new markets would tend to favour larger companies.

6. Conclusions and Outlook

The market of software to support materials R&D has been reviewed, including pertinent technologies for modelling, data, and informatics. The market remains quite heterogeneous and dynamic as advances in science and technology developments make it to market, including significant advances in ML/AI capabilities, professional lab informatics software geared to the advance in automation in materials laboratories, and nascent quantum computing for chemicals and materials software. Significant growth rates of $\approx 15\%$ CAGR are seen in the materials informatics market, evidenced by the fast growth of startup companies in the sector. Growth is likely to be driven further by the increasing focus on materials digitalisation as a means to respond to the need for accelerated development of advanced, safe and sustainable materials. (AMI2030, 2022)

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8. Disclaimer

All information contained in this study and any opinions expressed are intended to estimate the market share but are not a comment on a company's financial performance. All statements of fact, opinion, or analysis expressed in the report are those of Goldbeck Consulting. The information used and statements of fact made are not guarantees, warranties or representations as to their completeness or accuracy. Goldbeck Consulting assumes no liability for any short- or long-term decisions made as a result of the analysis included in this report.

9. Abbreviations

AEC - Architectural engineering and construction

AI - artificial intelligence

BSD - Berkeley Software Distribution

CAD – Computer-aided design

CAE – Computer-aided engineering

CAM – Computer-aided manufacturing

CAGR - Compound annual growth rate

EDA - Electronic design automation

FOSS – Free and open-source software

FTE – Full-time employee

FY - Financial year

GPL - GNU General Public License

ICSD - Inorganic Crystal Structure Database

LGPL - GNU Lesser General Public License

M&A – Merger and acquisition

MIT - a permissive free software license originating at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology

ML - machine learning

NIMS – National Institute for Materials Science, Japan's sole public research organization specialized in materials research

PLM - product lifecycle management

QSPR - Quantitative structure property relations

TAM – Total addressable market

TCAD - Technology computer-aided design, a branch of electronic design automation that models semiconductor fabrication and semiconductor device operation

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11. Appendix A: Methodology

11.1. General

As metrics of market size, we used a combination of the following:

- Published market size data
- Published revenue data
- Historical data about acquisitions of codes and their estimated growth
- Number of employees involved in materials modelling/informatics multiplied by a typical FTE cost.
- Estimated materials modelling share of continuum modelling products

Key assumptions are as follows:

- FTE cost: we assumed for each employee the company requires an income of €150k to cover salary and overheads and remain profitable.
- We only consider software providers (including some large distributors) but make no distinction between income based on software licenses and income from related services. Pure consulting and contract research providers are not included. Consequently, the considerable market related to industrial funding of consulting and projects at universities and research organisations is not included in this study.
- In Appendix A, an increase or decrease of FTEs is a result of diligent research and does not reflect the performance of an organisation.
- For currency conversions we applied the mid-market rates of 31st December 2022⁷.

11.2. Market Specific – Materials Modelling

Key assumptions are as follows:

- Materials modelling share of specific CAE products (continuum mechanics, fluid dynamics): Based on several private conversations, a reasonable assumption is that materials modelling accounts for between 5– 10% of relevant CAE software use. In the analysis below, we use 8% to determine the materials modelling share for general purpose continuum modelling software, and 5% for the materials modelling share of company revenue based on a range of CAE codes.

⁷ <https://www.xe.com/>

- For TCAD, we used the same 8% fraction that is related to materials modelling.
- From 2019–2022, we adopted, for all organisations covered in our 2019 report with a stable number of FTEs and no major acquisitions as revenue growth, a rate of 7% per annum, aligned with the CAGR Ansys reported to their shareholders as TAM for Ansys’ core simulation market (Ansys, 2022), which is in line with growth in the CAE market of 7.7% in 2020 reported by Fortune Business Insights⁸
- For six materials modelling companies we could use revenue as published in shareholder reports or government webpages. In particular, for Altair⁹ and Ansys¹⁰, we used their respective FY 2022 reports and estimated 5% of their business to be related to materials modelling because both include a mixture of CAD and CAE products. For ESI Group, we took 5% of their 2022 revenue as reported to their shareholders¹¹ to be related to materials modelling.
- We took our data from 2019 and added a 7% annual revenue growth to estimate the 2022 revenues for AutoDesk, AutoForm, Engineering Center Steyr GmbH & Co KG, Fujitsu, Hexagon, JSol Corporation, Schrödinger, Silvaco, and Synopsis.
- For COMSOL, we used a more recent number for the FTE value and applied an 8% CAE correction.
- With Dassault Systèmes (3DS) we researched the revenues for Simulia and FTEs of Biovia, respectively, to get insight into the income due to materials modelling.
- With Siemens Digital Industries Software, we took data from 2019 and added 7% annual revenue growth to estimate 2022 revenue, and added the revenue of Culgi (based on FTEs) because Siemens acquired Culgi in 2020. (Siemens, 2020).

11.3. Market Specific – Materials Informatics

For companies with a wide range of products (e.g., materials data bases, materials informatics, ML, and AI), we identified which of these featured strongest in their portfolio and grouped them into “AI and ML” and “Data”. Organisations that provide materials informatics, data, and ML/AI equally we grouped them as “materials informatics”.

Key assumptions are as follows:

- Estimated materials informatics share of cheminformatics products
- Materials informatic shares were determined from specific products the organisations offer or from their customer segments and case studies
- For Ansys, we estimated their share on the materials informatics market based on the turnover of Granta Design, which was acquired in 2019. (Dawson, 2019). For Dassault Systèmes, we investigated the number of FTEs of Biovia and estimated 10% of that revenue to be related to materials informatics.
- We also took the FTEs of Dotmatics and the informatics sector of PerkinElmer, Inc. and estimated both to have 20% of their revenue arising from materials informatics.

⁸ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/computer-aided-engineering-market-106891>

⁹ <https://investor.altair.com/news-releases/news-release-details/altair-announces-fourth-quarter-and-full-year-2022-financial>

¹⁰ <https://investors.ansys.com/news-releases/news-release-details/ansys-announces-financial-results-record-q4-and-fy-2022-acv>

¹¹ https://investors.esi-group.com/sites/default/files/prg/box/2171/DEU%202022_ENG.pdf

- For FIZ Karlsruhe and STN International, we considered the number of employees of their inorganic crystal structure data bases (ICSD) to estimate their revenue, and similarly, for National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), we looked at staff working for materials database.
- The organisations dedicated 100% to materials informatics in our study are Citrine Informatics, Dechema (Chemistry Data Series), Springer Materials, Total Materia, AI Materia, Albert, Dortmund Data Bank (DDBST GmbH), iChemLabs, Kebotix, Matelligence, Materials Zone, Matgenix, Matmerize, Phaseshift Technologies, Tilde Materials Informatics, and Uncountable. For the organisations, that are not solely dedicated to materials informatics, we took a percentage of their total revenue to be related to materials informatics, as reported in Appendix D.

12. Appendix B: Materials Modelling Software Providers

We assembled a list of 98 software companies (see Appendix B) working within the materials modelling field. We selected 18 large enterprises, five medium and 75 small software providers¹². The list is surely not exhaustive due to the large and constantly evolving number of small companies. Since our report in 2020, we have added three large, three medium and 25 small software providers. In particular, we added three continuum modelling companies not previously discussed: Applied Materials (based on FTEs and applied an 8% CAE correction), Aspen Technology (based on revenue reports and estimated 5% of their business to be related to materials modelling), and Cadence (based on their revenue and applied an 8% CAE correction)

12.1. Small Enterprises

Organisation	Modelling Type	Revenue estimation	Comments
Alphastar Cooperation	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/year
Asimptote	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/year
Avant-garde Materials Simulation*	Discrete	FTEs	new
BEASY	Continuum	FTEs	more FTEs
Ceondo*	Continuum	FTEs	new
ChemAlive*	Discrete	FTEs	new
Cogenda*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Collier Aerospace*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Computherm	Continuum	FTEs	fewer FTEs
COSMOS	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
Crosslight Software*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Crystal	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
CrystalMaker Software Ltd	Discrete	revenue	Higher revenue
DANTE	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	More FTEs
DCS Computing	Continuum	FTEs	More FTEs
Electricant	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Espeem	Discrete (STM)	FTEs	More FTEs
ESRD	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/ year
FaccTs	Discrete	FTEs	More FTEs

¹² Small, Medium and Large enterprises are defined by the number of employees up 50, 250, or higher, respectively, see also https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/business-friendly-environment/sme-definition_en

Fluxim*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Gaussian Inc	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
GlobalTCAD solutions	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	More FTEs
GTT	Continuum	FTEs	More FTEs
JPR Technologies*	Discrete	FTEs	new
Mat3ra	Discrete	FTEs	Fewer FTEs
MatCalc-Engineering	Continuum	FTEs	More FTEs
Materials Design	Discrete	Revenue	Higher Revenue
MaterialX*	Discrete (services)	FTEs	new
MATFEM Partnerschaft	Continuum	FTEs	Fewer FTEs
Math2Market	Continuum	revenue	Higher revenue
MicroMagus (General Numerics Research Lab)	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Molcas	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Molpro	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
MOLSIS Inc.	Discrete	FTEs	More FTEs
Nanomatch	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Nextmol*	Discrete	FTEs	new
nextnano GmbH*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
OneAngstrom*	Discrete	FTEs, 50% revenue = Materials	new
OptiLayer GmbH*	Continuum	revenue	new
Petachem	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ annum
Phaseshift Technologies*	Discrete	FTEs	new
ProSim	Continuum	Revenue, 8% CAE correction	Higher revenue
Q-Chem	Discrete	FTEs	More FTEs
QM Simulations Inc.	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Quantemol	Continuum	FTEs	More FTEs
Quantistry GmbH*	Discrete	FTEs	new
QuesTek Innovations LLC*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
QWED	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
RDMChem	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
RheoCube*	Discrete	FTEs	new
Robust Chip Inc*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Scienomics	discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
SCM	discrete	FTEs	More FTEs
Semichem Inc.	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Sente Software Ltd	Continuum	revenue	Higher revenue
Sentient Science*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Siborg Systems, Inc.*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Simon*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Simune Atomistic Simulations	Discrete	FTEs	fewer FTEs
SSA	Continuum	Revenue, 8% CAE correction	Higher revenue
STR Group*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
SuessCo Simulations	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
ThermoCalc	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Third Wave Systems	Continuum	FTEs	More FTEs
TIBERLAB	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/year
TotalSim*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new

Turbomole GmbH	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
VASP Software GmbH	Discrete	Based on 2019	7% growth/year
Vextec	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	More FTEs
Virtual Lab	Discrete	FTEs	More FTEs
Wavefunction	Discrete	FTEs	fewer FTEs
WebMO*	Discrete	FTEs	new
Wien2k	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
X-Ability	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year
Zacros	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/year

12.2. Medium Enterprises

Organisation	Modelling Type	Revenue Estimation	Comment
Access e.V.	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/year
Coventor*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Cresset*	Discrete	FTEs, take 10% Materials	new
SimScale*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Transvalor	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/ year

12.3. Large Enterprises

Organisation	Modelling Type	Revenue Estimation	Comment
Altair	Continuum	Revenue, 5% materials related	Higher revenue
Ansys	Continuum	Revenue, 5% materials related	Higher revenue
Applied Materials*	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	new
Aspen Technology*	Continuum	Revenue, 5% materials related	new
AutoDesk	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/ year
AutoForm	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/ year
Cadence*	Continuum	Revenue, 8% CAE correction	new
COMSOL	Continuum	FTEs, 8% CAE correction	More FTEs
Dassault Systèmes (3DS)	both	Revenue, 8% CAE correction plus Biovia revenue	More accurate data
Engineering Center Steyr GmbH & Co KG	Continuum	based on 2019, 8% CAE correction	7% growth/ year
ESI Group	Continuum	Revenue, 5% materials related	Higher revenue
Fujitsu	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Hexagon	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
JSol Corporation	both	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Schrödinger	Discrete	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Siemens Digital Industries Software	both	based on 2019	7% growth/ year plus Culgi revenue based on FTEs
Silvaco	Continuum	based on 2019	7% growth/ year
Synopsys	both	based on 2019	7% growth/ year

12.4. Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS)

The FOSS Electronic Modelling Market

Table 1 Electronic FOSS software, its licensing, and links to the respective websites

Code (*added in 2022)	License	Info
Abinit	GPL	https://www.abinit.org/
CASTEP	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	http://www.castep.org/Main/HomePage
CONQUEST	MIT	http://www.order-n.org/
CP2K	GPL	https://www.cp2k.org/
DALTON	LGPL v2	https://daltonprogram.org/
deMon2k	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	http://www.demon-software.com/public_html/index.html
Fleur	MIT	http://www.flapw.de/MaX-4.0/
Gamess*	proprietary license at no cost	https://www.msg.chem.iastate.edu/gamess/index.html
NEMO-3D	LGPL v2	https://engineering.purdue.edu/gekcogrp/software-projects/nemo3D/
NWChem	Educational Community License 2.0, like Apache	https://nwchemgit.github.io/
OpenMX	GPL v3	http://www.openmx-square.org/
QuantumEspresso	GPL	https://www.quantum-espresso.org/
Siesta	GPL	https://departments.icmab.es/leem/siesta/
The Elk Code	GPL	http://elk.sourceforge.net/
Yambo	GPL	http://www.yambo-code.org/

These codes are supported by an estimated investment of €18.5 m.

The FOSS Atomistic Modelling Market

Table 2 Atomistic FOSS software, its licensing, and links to the respective websites

Code	License	Info
DL AKMC	LGPL	http://www.ccp5.ac.uk/DL_AKMC/
DL Monte	BSD	https://www.ccp5.ac.uk/DL_MONTE
DL Poly	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	https://www.scd.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/DL_POLY.aspx
GROMACS	GPL/LGPL	http://www.gromacs.org/
GULP	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	https://gulp.curtin.edu.au/gulp/news.cfm
LAMMPS	GPL	https://lammps.sandia.gov/
NAMD	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	https://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Research/namd/
Py-ChemShell	LGPL 3	https://www.chemshell.org/documentation
Tinker	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	https://dasher.wustl.edu/tinker/
Vampire	GPL	https://vampire.york.ac.uk/

These codes are supported by an estimated investment of €8.5 m.

The FOSS Mesoscopic Modelling Market

Table 3 Mesoscopic FOSS software, its licensing, and links to the respective websites

Code	License	Info
DL Meso	Proprietary	https://www.scd.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/DL_MESO.aspx
ESPResSo-Extensible Simulation Package for REsearch on Soft Matter	GPL v3	http://espressomd.org/wordpress/
HOOMD-blue	BSD	http://glotzerlab.engin.umich.edu/hoomd-blue/
LIGGGHTS	GPL v2	https://www.cfdem.com/liggghts-open-source-discrete-element-method-particle-simulation-code
OCTA	Proprietary free	http://octa.jp/#intro
ParaDis	LGPL	http://paradis.stanford.edu/
Quasicontinuum	GPL v2	http://qcmethod.org/

These codes are supported by an estimated investment of €5.1 m.

The FOSS Continuum Modelling Market

Table 4 Continuum FOSS software, its licensing, and links to the respective websites

Code (*added in 2022)	License	Info
Aestimo 1D*	GPL v3	https://www.aestimosolver.org
Archimedes*	GPL	http://www.gnu.org/software/archimedes/
Calculix	LGPL	http://www.dhondt.de/
Cantera	Proprietary free	https://cantera.org/
CatalyticFoam	GPL v3	http://www.catalyticfoam.polimi.it/
Charon Device Simulator*	GPL	https://charon.sandia.gov
Code Aster	GPL	https://code-aster.org
Code Saturne	GPL v2	https://www.code-saturne.org
Damask	GPL v3	https://damask.mpie.de/bin/view/Home/WebHome
DEVSIM Open Source TCAD Software *	Apache 2.0 License	https://devsim.org
ECORCE*	GPL v3	http://ecorce2d.free.fr/
Elmer FEM	LGPL	http://www.elmerfem.org/blog/
Erwin Jr*	GPL	https://erwinjr.org/
FLOOXs*	Proprietary, Acad free, comm Fee	http://www.flooxs.ece.ufl.edu/index.php/Manual
Genius TCAD Open*	GPL	https://github.com/cogenda/Genius-TCAD-Open
Goma	GPL	https://www.gomafem.com/
nano-Archimedes*	GPL	http://www.nano-archimedes.com
NanoTCAD ViDES*	BDS	http://vides.nanotcad.com/
NEMO-3D*	free, must join user group	https://engineering.purdue.edu/gekcogrp/software-projects/nemo3D/
OBPDS*	AGPL v3	https://github.com/scott-maddox/obpds
OEDES*	AGPL v3	https://github.com/mzszym/oedes
OghmaNano*	GPL v2, MIT	https://www.oghma-nano.com/
OpenFoam	GPL	https://www.openfoam.com/
OpenPhase Core	GPL v3	https://openphase-solutions.com/

Peridigm	BSD	https://peridigm.sandia.gov/
Quantum Wells, Wires and Dots*	GPL v3	https://sourceforge.net/projects/qwwad/
SALOME	LGPL	https://www.salome-platform.org/
SOLCORE*	GPL v3	https://www.solcore.solar/

These codes are supported by an estimated minimum investment of €3.9 m.

13. Appendix C: Quantum Computing Enterprises

Organisation	Size	Info
HQS	medium	https://quantumsimulations.de
Molecular Quantum Solutions	small	https://mqs.dk/
QC Ware	medium	https://www.qcware.com/
Quantinuum	large	https://www.quantinuum.com/
Quantum Generative Materials (GenMat)	small	https://www.genmat.xyz/

14. Appendix D: Materials Informatics Software Providers

14.1. Small Enterprises

Organisation	Major Product Line	% of their revenue arising from materials informatics
AI Materia	ML/AI	100 %
Albert	Materials Informatics	100 %
CCDC	Data	75 %
CMCL Innovations	Materials Informatics	10 %
DataStories	Materials Informatics	8 %
Dortmund Data Bank (DDBST GmbH)	Data	100 %
Edelweiss Connect	Cheminformatics	5 %
iChemLabs	Materials Informatics	100 %
Intellegens	ML/AI	75 %
Kebotix	Materials Informatics	100 %
Matelligence	ML/AI	100 %
Materials Zone	Materials Informatics	100 %
Matgenix	Materials Informatics	100 %
Matmatch	Data	75 %
Matmerize	Materials Informatics	100 %
Mipar	ML/AI	20 %
Noble AI	ML/AI	20 %
Phaseshift Technologies	Materials Informatics	100 %
Tilde Materials Informatics	Materials Informatics	100 %
Uncountable	Materials Informatics	100 %

14.2. Medium Enterprises

Organisation	Major Product Line	% of their revenue arising from materials informatics
ACD/Labs	Cheminformatics	20 %
Chemaxon	Cheminformatics	10 %
Chemical.ai	ML/AI	10 %
Citrine Informatics	ML/AI	100 %
Collaborative Drug Discovery Inc. (CDD)	Cheminformatics	5 %
Dechema	Data	100 %
Enthought	Materials Informatics	50 %
Esteco	Materials Informatics	10 %
Molecular Networks GmbH	Materials Informatics	50 %
Open Eye	Cheminformatics	10 %
Springer Materials	Data	100 %
Total Materia	Data	100 %

14.3. Large Enterprises

Organisation	Major Product Line	% of their revenue arising from materials informatics
Ansys/Granta	Materials Informatics	100%
Dotmatics	Cheminformatics	20%
DS3 Biovia	Cheminformatics	10%
Fiz Karlsruhe and STN International	Data	consider 100% ICSD
IDBS	Cheminformatics	10%
NIMS	Data	100%
PerkinElmer, Inc.	Materials Informatics	20%